

topAM BRIEFING

Developing ODS high temperature alloys tailored for AM

This topAM Briefing covers the latest project results including: modelling of the dispersoids, powder modifications, AM production of samples, and materials properties of the modified alloys.

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WP2 Optimal computational design for LPBF based on ICME

With dispersing particles successfully introduced to the base alloys, WP2 has taken experimental feedback from other WPs to calibrate and validate ICME models for improved confidence in predictions. Figure 1 exemplifies particle size evolution simulations of TiN in modified Alloy 400 comparing cooling rates for casting and laser-based additive manufacturing

(AM) with experimental data points for validation. The predicted average particle size after AM is sub-micron or nano scale, compared with micron scale in castings. These precipitation simulations enable AM process design and optimization.

Figure 1. Prediction of average particle radius with different solidification cooling rates, validated by experimental observation of TiN particles in the as-deposited modified Alloy 400 (experimental details can be found in Roth et al., Mater. Sci. Eng. A, 893 (2024) 146129), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2024.146129>

WP3 LPBF component design

In WP3, an in-house OpenFOAM solver for the multiphysics optimization using the continuous adjoint approach has been developed and validated using literature. The capabilities of the standard optimization

solver of OpenFOAM are extended by the inclusion of the heat transfer equation. Currently, artificial intelligence (AI) acceleration is being integrated within the developed solver using neural networks (Figure 2).

Figure 2. (a) Benchmark manifold case with one inlet and four outlets, (b) Results from the conjugate heat transfer (CHT) simulation after topology optimization for velocity distribution, (c) Predicted result for velocity distribution using AI.

WP4 Powder production and modification

Amongst the many powder modification routes developed and tested in topAM, the final, most promising ones could be narrowed down. The three approaches, namely extensive Yttria mixing (see Figure 3 for the process scheme), internal nitridation via the fluidized bed reactor (FBR) and internal nitridation during atomization via gas atomization reaction synthesis (GARS) (developed at RISE, La Rochelle University and Indutherm GmbH, respectively) clearly stood out and revealed high

potential for the Ni- and NiCu-based alloys investigated. As displayed in Figure 4, the successful deposition of Yttria on the surface of an Alloy 400 powder particle via the extensive mixing approach is clearly recognizable. Further processed via laser powder bed fusion (LPBF), these homogeneously dispersed nanoparticles will contribute to an enhanced strengthening within additively manufactured parts due to the Orowan mechanism.

Figure 3. Process scheme of the Extensive Mixing process with Yttria.

Figure 4. STEM-EDS analysis revealing the presence of Yttria on the Alloy 400 powder surface.

As the final modifications of choice have now been found, the last few atomization are currently carried out in order to supply the sufficient modified powders for final component manufacturing to the material printing institutes (RWTH-DAP and Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences, respectively). In terms of the NiCu-based heat exchanger components, Alloy 400 is being produced and modified via the FBR internal nitridation approach. For the Ni-based Alloy

699XA instead, the nitrogen GARS modification revealed the highest potential which is why further powder is currently generated via this production method. Besides some powder characterization tasks remaining, the WP4 activities within topAM are now coming to an end and the focus is set on the AM production of final component for the rest of the project duration.

WP5 LPBF and Post-Processing

WP5 activities have been focused on optimizing the LPBF-process for a variety of powders that have undergone diverse modification routes. Upon working closely with WP4 and WP6, material data sheets for promising alloys that exhibited significant enhancements in mechanical properties during preliminary testing have been developed. Following an extensive process development phase, promising alloy modifications have been identified for Ni-based and NiCu alloy systems.

The observations indicate a prevailing trend favoring in-situ modification methods, such as internal oxidation and nitridation during atomization (pioneered by Indutherm, Germany), as well as post-internal oxidation and nitridation in a FBR (developed at La

Rochelle University, France), in terms of mechanical properties and short-term corrosion performance. However, a newly devised ex-situ modification technique known as extensive mixing, developed at RISE research institutes in Sweden, demonstrated promising results in terms of processability as well as mechanical properties in tensile, fatigue, and creep tests, particularly for Ni-based alloys.

At present, WP5 is primarily engaged in planning the manufacturing of final components using selected modified alloys and optimized process parameters. The necessary quantity of powder for manufacturing these components has already been communicated to the powder manufacturing partners, while designs are being finalized in WP3.

Figure 5. EBSD analysis reveals partial recrystallization in modified Nickel-based 699 alloy processed via LPBF. This alloy was ex-situ modified with 1% Y_2O_3 using the Extensive Mixing method, followed by heat treatment at 1275°C for 1 hour. Short-term mechanical tests demonstrated notably enhanced performance compared to the base alloy and comparable to in-situ modification routes.

WP6 Material properties

All long-term tests for various modified oxide-dispersion strengthened (ODS) materials are currently running in different atmospheres: molten nitrate salts, oxidation in steam, metal dusting and oxidation in dry air. While data compilation is ongoing, the final outcomes will be released by the last quarter of the year. As an example, unmodified 699XA made by AM show good performances in dry air, comparable to that of 699 hot rolled material.

The current results up to 1000h of exposure at 950°C (Figure 6a), indicate the establishment of parabolic kinetics of oxidation for all AM modification after

different initial mass uptakes. This shows that the microstructure and the chemistry of AM 699XA can be customized by LPBF. Both the unmodified and ODS modified 699XA show good compatibility with the application of slurry Al and Al/Si protective coatings developed by La Rochelle University (Figure 6b) allowing to dramatically decrease the mass gains.

Corrosion tests are essential for the proof of principle (WP7), and for feedback into the alloy modelling (WP2). As the property results become available, they are also being compared with the target performance indicators (TPIs).

Figure 6. Evolution of the specific mass gains with time of the additive manufactured and hot rolled 699XA alloy at 950°C (left) and oxidation reduction provided by the Al and the Al/Si slurry coatings (right).

WP7 Proof of principle

Burners for partial oxidation are fired with pure oxygen and feed (natural gas) at sub stoichiometric ratios. The burner has two concentric burner ports at the burner tip. Oxygen is added via the central tip which for the proof of principle will be manufactured from modified Alloy 602CA. The outer ring-shaped port for the feed injection will be manufactured from modified Alloy 699XA. This part will include channels to pass cooling water close to the tip of the burner. The two AM parts will be welded to an existing burner which will be cut to length. A compensator will be installed in the oxygen

line to meet the defined ring shape at the tip of the burner.

The burner will be tested in a test furnace (see Figure 7). The furnace operates at atmospheric pressure and additional oxygen is added at the end of the furnace to ensure complete combustion before the flue gases will be released to the atmosphere. Measurement equipment and special cameras are available to monitor the burner operation during the test.

Figure 7. Picture of the test furnace at Linde Gas Unterschleißheim, where the burner tests for the proof of principle will be performed.

WP8 Dissemination, communication, exploitation

The topAM communication activities on LinkedIn, X (former Twitter) and our webpage continued.

We are also pleased that the project has already led to seven publications. We invite you to view these at:

Influence of surface treatment on the metal dusting behavior of Alloy 699 XA. E. White, C. Schlereth, M. Lepple, H. Hattendorf, B. Nowak, M. C. Galetz, <https://doi.org/10.1002/maco.202213380>

Comparison of Microstructure and Properties of Nickel-Copper Alloy Prepared by Casting and Laser Powder Bed Fusion Process. A. Chlupová, I. Šulák, I. Kuběna, T. Kruml, J.-P. Roth, K. Jahns, <https://doi.org/10.4028/p-884q32>

An Expanded Model for the Pressure Effect in Metal Dusting of Mn-containing Alloy 600 Based on Advanced Scale Characterization. M.C. Galetz, C. Schlereth, E.M.H. White, T. Boll, M. Bik, M. Sitarz, W.-T. Chen, B. Gleeson, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11085-023-10201-2>

Understanding the mechanism of columnar-to-equiaxed transition and grain refinement in additively manufactured steel during laser powder bed fusion. Venkatesh Pandian Narayana Samy, Moritz Schäfle, Frederike Brasche, Christian Haase, Ulrich Krupp, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2023.103702>

The dispersion-strengthening effect of TiN evoked by in situ nitridation of NiCu-based Alloy 400 during gas atomization for laser powder bed fusion. J.-P. Roth, I. Šulák, Z. Chlup, J. Fischer-Bühner, U. Krupp, K. Jahns, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2024.146129>

Fatigue lifetime assessment and crack propagation of Ni-based alloy VDM 699 XA produced by additive manufacturing. Tomáš Vražina, Ivo Šulák, Benedikt Nowak, Bhupesh Verma, Ulrich Krupp, Tomáš Kruml, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2023.12.005>

High-temperature Fatigue and Creep Performance of Additively Manufactured NiCu-based Alloy. Ivo Šulák, Alice Chlupová, Tomáš Záležák, Ivo Kuběna, Jan-Philipp Roth, Katrin Jahns, Ulrich Krupp, Tomáš Kruml, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2023.12.015>

topAM General Assembly Meeting and topAM fall school, 28-30 October 2024, Gothenburg, Sweden

We are happy to announce the next topAM General Assembly meeting in October, hosted by RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. In conjunction with the final topAM fall school will take place.

The topAM schools educate students about the fundamentals of topAM related topics, new methods developed in topAM, and recent results. The fall school intends to provide knowledge on new topAM findings and technologies for students at an early career stage. We believe that educating young researchers helps accelerating cross-disciplinary approaches and supports the dissemination of results. The topAM schools are designed as a mixture of lectures, workshops, lab-visits, and hands-on- training.

This topAM fall school is organized for students from our partner institutes but will be open for the application of other students as well.

The agenda and application forms will be soon available at: <https://www.aspire2050.eu/topam>

Visit us at MSE Congress 2024!

At the MSE Congress 2024 (Materials Science and Engineering) on 24-26 September 2024, which takes place in Darmstadt, Germany and online, the topAM project will organise a special symposium.

Under the topic “Functional Materials, Surfaces and Devices”, the **Special Symposium F02: “High Performance Materials for Sustainable Energy Applications”** will be organised by the coordinators of the funded projects under the LC-SPIRE-08-2020 call, e.g. Professor Ulrich Krupp, RWTH-IEHK, coordinator of topAM.

This symposium will address recent advances in the field of novel high performance materials and components (**according to aims of projects under the Horizon 2020 framework under, call LC-SPIRE-08-2020**) by addressing materials design concepts, new materials as bulk materials or as coatings (metallic and ceramic), and technologies for their development, with the final aim of manufacturing components for the industrial applications.

[Link to the Special Symposium.](#)